

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILDREN FOR FORMATION OF
DEVELOPMENT FOR PREPARATION FOR UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: the article reveals educational psychology or educational psychology - a branch of psychology that studies methods of teaching and upbringing that increase the efficiency of fulfilling educational tasks, the effectiveness of pedagogical measures, improving the psychological aspects of teaching, etc. Professional development occurs within the framework of one or another professional activity, which differs from general human development and personality development, a systemic characteristic of the mental development of a child of senior preschool age, which includes the formation of abilities and properties that provide the opportunity for him to carry out educational activities, as well as the adoption of the social position of the schoolchild.

Key words: human development/ ability to develop/ interaction with the profession/ student activities/ chosen profession.

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ ДЛЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ
РАЗВИТИЯ К ПОДГОТОВКЕ В ВУЗ

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Аннотация: в статье раскрывается педагогическая психология или психология образования - раздел психологии, изучающий методы обучения и воспитания, повышающие эффективность выполнения образовательных задач, эффективность педагогических мер, улучшающие психологические аспекты преподавания и т. Профессиональное развитие происходит в рамках той или иной профессиональной деятельности, чем и отличается от общего развития человека и развития личности, системная характеристика психического развития ребёнка старшего дошкольного возраста, которая включает в себя сформированность способностей и свойств, обеспечивающих возможность выполнения им учебной деятельности, а также принятие социальной позиции школьника.

Ключевые слова: развитие человека/ способность к развитию/ взаимодействию с профессией/ деятельность школьника/ избранная профессия.

The components of psychological readiness to study at a university are motivational, social-personal, intellectual and emotional-volitional readiness. Personal and professional development is the process of development of the subject of professional work and the formation of professional self-determination, the result of vocational education. Professional development is changes in a person's mental functions and properties that arise during interaction with a profession, in the process of professional training and professional activity. Professional development occurs within the framework of one or another professional activity, which is why it differs from the general development of a person and the development of personality, and it is

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determined by the content, requirements, and conditions of the professional activity being mastered.

The formation of a subject of activity is not completed until the activity is carried out; This is a kind of permanent process that applies to any age of a person as a doer. Data from numerous studies have shown that late completion of professional activity acts as a factor in increasing life expectancy. During the period of adulthood, the types of activities that are leading at the previous stages of individual development (communication, exploration of the objective world, play, learning, organizational and social activities, work, etc.) are integrated and give rise to different types of combined ways of human life. It is during the period of adulthood that a person's transition of cardinal importance occurs from the stage of solving the life tasks assigned to him to the stage of posing new problems, to the formulation of qualitatively new tasks. Thus, the development of a person as a subject of professional life can be considered as a complex process that combines ontogeny and a person's life path. Studying the process of a person's professional development means studying a developing person in a complex, changing environment, including a professional one. The process of professional development is characterized by stages, unevenness, heterochrony, the presence of critical and sensitive periods, that is, it is characterized by the same patterns as ontogenetic development. Thus, the problem of professional development is considered by both psychologists and teachers in the context of the processes of professionalization, professional activity and professional development.

In addition, you cannot stand still in the profession; skills and functions sometimes require an upgrade. Experienced and prudent managers strive to avoid problems by proactively developing an individual professional development plan for each employee. This approach is beneficial both for the boss, for the subordinates, and for the business as a whole. Youth is a socio-demographic group, which is characterized by a combination of psychological and age characteristics (from 16 to 35 years), periods of formation of social maturity, entry into the world of adults, adaptation to it and its future renewal.

It is important, however, to understand that drawing up a long-term plan for professional development in a situation influenced by a large number of external factors is not an easy job. The motivational-semantic component in the psychological structure of professionally significant personality traits is interconnected with the processes of a specialist's broad understanding of acquired professional knowledge, responsible choice of methods of personal behavior and professional activity, which ultimately reveals the content of the professional orientation of the specialist's personality.

Only with a serious investment of the manager's time and personal resources can one expect high-quality returns.

The development of professionally significant personality traits in future specialists in the context of vocational education characterizes them from the point of view of scientific-theoretical, moral and behavioral-volitional readiness for professional activity, competent, socially oriented life activity in society. As signs of readiness for professional activity, scientists consider the degree of formation in a person of the main mental regulators of activity: "image of an object" (subjective image of the profession); "image of the subject" (image of the Self - self-consciousness); "the image of subject-subject and subject-object relations" (professional self-awareness).

First of all, the student's professional movement must be purposeful, planned and a plan for his progress for the next 1 - 3 years or 3 - 5 years. It should set out qualification requirements and steps for career advancement.

Ideally, each individual movement should include:

it is necessary to name those that satisfy the completeness of the student;

determine the positions that require strengthening and the deadlines within which everything must be completed;

list what studies will allow you to develop the necessary skills;

plan introductory internships for reserve areas of a certain profession, write down the expected result;

include in your personal folder a plan for delegating some responsibilities from backup areas;

in the personal schedule there should be monitoring and analysis of the student's development, provide a mark of the fact of fulfillment of the planned actions of readiness to enter a university and specific terms of preparation.

Human development occurs in the process of learning, self-knowledge, social interaction and accumulation of experience, which is formed throughout life, and preparation for entering a university is considered the main period of a student's life.

LITERATURES USED:

1. Бодров В. А. Исследование структуры и динамики летных способностей / В.А. Бодров, Ю.Э. Писаренко // Психол. журнал. 1995. Т. 6. № 2. С. 85-94;
2. Борисова Е. М. О роли профессиональной деятельности в формировании личности // Психология формирования и развития личности / Отв. ред. Л. И. Анцыферова. М., 1981. С. 159-176;
3. Климов Е. А. Введение в психологию труда. М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1988. 199 с.; Марищук В. Л. Психологические основы формирования профессионально значимых качеств: Дис. ... д-ра психол. наук. Л., 1982. 351 с.;
4. Ростунов А.Т. Формирование профессиональной пригодности. Минск, 1984. 176 с.;
5. Рожкова А. П. Развитие личностных профессионально важных качеств студентов-психологов средствами тренинга: Дис. ... канд. психол. наук. М., 2003.
6. Гуревич К. М. Профессиональная пригодность и основные свойства нервной системы. М., 1979; Левитов Д. Н. Психология труда. М., 1963; Смирнов А. А. О психологической подготовке к труду // Избранные психологические труды. М. 1987. Т. 1. С. 229-241.
7. Дружилов С. А. Системный подход к изучению психологического феномена профессионализма человека // Вестник Томского Педагогического университета. 2005. Вып. 1 (45). Серия: Психология С. 51-55.
8. Ермакова З. В. Профессиональная идентичность социального педагога: Дис. ... канд. психол. наук. Владивосток, 2007. С. 14.
9. Иванова Н. Л., Конева Е. В. Социальная идентичность и профессиональный опыт личности. Ярославль, 2003. С. 52-53.
10. Климов Е.А. Образ мира в разнотипных профессиях: Уч. пособие. М.: МГУ, 1995. С. 9.

11. Маркова А. К. Психология профессионализма. М.: МГУ, 1996. 308 с.
12. Петренко В. Ф. Введение в экспериментальную психосемантику: исследование форм репрезентации в обыденном сознании. М., 1983.
13. Поваренков Ю. П. Развитие и диагностика способностей / Отв. ред. В. Н. Дружинин, В. Д. Шадриков. М.: Наука, 1991. С. 107.
14. Нозимов Ж.Т., Усманова М.Н. [Социально-психологические аспекты интернет-зависимости среди студентов](#). Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические...
15. М.Н. Усманова, Ж.Т. Нозимов. [Социально-психологические механизмы интернет зависимости у студентов](#). Наука и образование 3 (5), 1299-1305.
16. Ж.Т. Нозимов. [Использование тренингов в развитии межкультурной компетентности у студентов](#). Психология образования будущего: от традиций к инновациям, 112-114.

